

PCP WISE

D2.1 Communication strategy and communication toolkit

WP2 Impact Maximisation
G.A.C. Group

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Document abstract

The present document *D2.1 Communication strategy and toolkit* is the first deliverable part of Work Package 2 – Impact maximisation of the PCP WISE project. This deliverable intends to present an overall strategy dedicated to raising awareness about PCP WISE, engaging with relevant target audiences identified, promoting the project and its results. A sound communication and dissemination (C&D) strategy will be set in motion, notably via different networks the project identified across the thematic areas covered by the project and its five application domains. This document identifies objectives, responsibilities and metrics set for ensuring a swift implementation of communication and dissemination activities. It also presents relevant tools and channels for communication and dissemination, and it serves the purpose of defining a communication toolkit composed of the project logo, templates and communication and dissemination material.

Keywords

Communication strategy, dissemination, outreach, social media strategy, communication toolkit, target group, awareness raising, impact

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
EO	Environmental Observation
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PCP	Pre-Commercial Procurement
PCP WISE	Pre-Commercial Procurement for Water Intelligence from Space for European climate resilience
R&I	Research & Innovation
VC	Venture Capital
WP	Work Package

1. At a glance

Communication and dissemination are of paramount importance to the success and impact of the **Pre-Commercial Procurement for Water Intelligence from Space for European climate resilience (PCP WISE)** project. Continuously sharing internal and external information is a transversal element that should be smoothly conducted throughout the project, and which should consider all communities relevant for and possibly interested in the project.

The PCP WISE Communication strategy aims to capitalise on Horizon 2020- and Horizon Europe-funded projects' communication best practices and follow a **6W approach: What, Why, When, hoW, Where and to Whom** communicate and disseminate.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a reference document for strategically and effectively communicating and disseminating information throughout the PCP WISE project. This document claims to go a step further than what was described in PCP WISE's Description of Action, in terms of what should be done to ensure effective communication of the project's objectives, activities, and its outcomes. It defines the primary target audiences for communication in importantly, it builds on the communication and dissemination work done during the **PROTECT** project¹, the Coordination and Support Action funded by the European Commission to prepare the ground for the PCP WISE project.

Communication and dissemination are key levers to maximise the impact of the project. They are nevertheless two different concepts. **Communication** is about increasing the visibility of the project, while **dissemination** is about preparing the ground for the exploitation of the project results. In this communication strategy plan only communication channels and tools used to further disseminate knowledge and information are addressed.

This deliverable also provides a **reference communication toolkit** for partners and external stakeholders in supporting PCP WISE communication activities. It is a guide for project partners on how best to promoting the project and maximising its impact using the right communication tools and channels.

Finally, this report informs about the **roles and responsibilities** of PCP WISE partners related to communication activities and identifies the target audiences and the key messages that should be adapted and delivered to them. The communication activities **monitoring and evaluation approach and KPIs** are also described in this report.

¹ <https://www.protect-pcp.eu/>

2. Introduction

2.1. Project overview

PCP WISE is a collaborative initiative leveraging **Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) and Earth Observation (EO)** data to enhance water management and climate resilience. It aims to customise/pre-operationalise water management innovations from space for European climate resilience via the PCP approach. The project, spanning from solution design to field validation, targets TRL 8. It addresses water-related crises (floods, fires and infrastructure impacts) using space and EO data.

Among the objectives foreseen within the project, it is included a common operational information product, interoperability mechanisms, and an active user network. With climate change impacting water availability and distribution, PCP WISE seeks to enhance EO-based information for better regional water management, promoting resilience across EU borders. It focuses on local dynamics in water availability and aims to anticipate extreme climate conditions through an integrated water intelligence system.

The project's significance lies in its potential to mitigate water-related crises, driven by a unified water taxonomy and EO-based modelling. Through comprehensive research and development solutions, PCP WISE aims to boost adaptation across the EU, targeting stakeholders in water management, environment, first responders, cities, and agriculture.

The project's objectives are designed to address business, technical, economic, and policy goals. Key results include capacity-building efforts, climate-related inputs, stakeholder engagement, and the dissemination of innovative solutions to advance water resilience both locally and globally.

2.2. Why communication matters?

Effective communication is a critical success factor for the PCP WISE project, ensuring that its objectives, methodologies, and outcomes reach the right stakeholders and drive meaningful impact. Given the project's focus on PCP and the use of EO data for water management, clear and strategic communication is essential to raise awareness about these innovative approaches. Among others, public buyers, policymakers, and technology providers need to understand how PCP can enhance climate resilience and why EO-based solutions offer a transformative approach to tackling water-related challenges such as floods and wildfires. Without a well-structured communication strategy, the project risks being seen as a niche initiative rather than a scalable and replicable model for sustainable procurement.

Beyond raising awareness, **communication is key to fostering stakeholder engagement and collaboration** (expected to be further developed as part of D2.2 and D2.5). PCP WISE brings together a diverse ecosystem of actors, including public authorities, research institutions, industry players, and policymakers, each with different levels of expertise and priorities. **A tailored communication approach** ensures that these groups remain actively involved,

contributing insights, feedback, and support for the project's long-term success. **Engaging stakeholders early and consistently** increases the likelihood of policy uptake, market adoption, and replicability of PCP-based procurement models across Europe. Additionally, **clear and transparent communication** builds trust, ensuring that public buyers and suppliers see the project as a credible and valuable initiative.

Finally, **communication plays a pivotal role in impact maximization and knowledge transfer**. PCP WISE is not just about developing innovative water management solutions, it is also about mainstreaming PCP as a viable procurement model. Effective storytelling, knowledge dissemination, and targeted outreach help demystify the PCP process, making it more accessible to procurement professionals unfamiliar with its benefits. **By leveraging multi-channel communication** (website, social media, workshops, policy briefs), **PCP WISE can inspire other public authorities to explore demand-driven innovation**.

What is the difference between communication, dissemination, and exploitation in the context of Horizon Europe²?

Communication means informing, promoting and communicating on the project activities and results in reaching out to multiple audiences (citizens, the media, etc.). Communication therefore requires having a well-designed strategy, conveying clear messages, and using the right communication channels from the very start of the project and until its end.

Dissemination is about making the results of the project public and available to all stakeholders who can learn about and possibly be interested in using the results of the project. Such stakeholders can include but are not limited to public authorities, industry, policymakers, sectors of interest, civil society etc. Dissemination can translate into the publication of project results in scientific magazines, scientific or targeted conferences and events, and databases.

Exploitation serves to make concrete use of project results for commercial, societal and/or political purposes. Exploitation of results can be performed by researchers, industry, and generally all stakeholders that can make use of them including public authorities, industrial authorities, policymakers, civil society etc. Exploitation activities can take the form of roadmap, prototypes and software creation, as well as knowledge, skills and data sharing. It usually takes place towards the end of the project and beyond but can be activated as soon as the project has produced exploitable results.

Communication, dissemination, and exploitation of project results are closely intertwined. Communication and dissemination can make use of the same tools and channels while addressing different audiences for different matters. Dissemination prepares the use, i.e., the future exploitation of project results as it raises awareness among key target groups, which might later become involved in the exploitation paths of certain project results. This report therefore describes elements which can address at least two of these aspects at the same time, while making clear what the distinguishing elements are.

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https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation_en#the-complementary-role-of-communication

3. Communication strategy

3.1. Overall strategy

The PCP WISE Communication Strategy goal is to effectively disseminate information, engage stakeholders, and maximise the project's visibility and impact. To do so, the proposed communication (and dissemination, expected at M6) strategy will follow a **6W approach** to ensure that every communication and dissemination opportunity in the future is adequately exploited during and by the project.

The 6W strategy aims to clearly identify:

- **Why communicate and disseminate:** For efficient communication and dissemination activities, the first point to be identified are the objectives of the communication and dissemination
- **To Whom to communicate and disseminate:** Different communication and dissemination objectives will have to target different audiences; these different audiences must be defined
- **What to communicate and disseminate:** Different audiences have different interests and needs and will need to be addressed with different key messages defined according to the expected outcomes and impacts of the project
- **How to communicate and disseminate:** Different audiences must be reached and addressed through different channels. To be efficient, communication and dissemination activities must be well-coordinated and monitored
- **Where to communicate and disseminate:** To fully reach its objectives, the project must communicate and disseminate to all its target audiences and all over Europe; and
- **When to communicate and disseminate:** The project communication and dissemination must both run throughout the duration of the project, with long lasting and scheduled actions, and take advantage of opportunities that may arise during the project.

Therefore, this report starts with identifying the dissemination and communication objectives of the PCP WISE project, answering the **Why** disseminate question in **section 2.2**. This report also further defines the project's key target audiences and associated messages in **section 3.3**, answering hereby the **to Whom** and **What** questions.

Based on the identified targeted audiences, **section 4** additionally answers the **What** to disseminate/communicate questions describing the various project communication and dissemination tools and channels, and providing more details on opportune communication activities, listing among others the events and networking activities planned until M7 of the project, thereby answering the **Where** and **When** to disseminate/communicate questions. This point will be described in details in deliverable D2.2 Dissemination Plan due at M6.

Finally, **section 5** answers the **how to disseminate/communicate** question describing the roles and responsibilities of project partners, together with the processes and procedures to

be followed for planning, coordinating and monitoring communication and dissemination activities.

3.2. Communication objectives

To produce a coherent and efficient communication strategy, the first question to be answered is **Why should we communicate? What are the communication objectives of the project?**

Section **2.2 2.2Why communication matters?** already provides a rationale for a sound PCP WISE communication strategy. With this in mind, PCP WISE communication strategy is designed to ensure widespread awareness, engagement, and impact maximisation of the project's activities, methodologies, and results. Also, given that PCP WISE promotes PCP as an innovative tool for advancing water management solutions using EO data, its success depends on effectively communicating with a diverse range of stakeholders, including public buyers, policymakers, technology providers, and the general public.

To achieve this, the communication strategy is structured around the following four key specific communication objectives.

3.2.1. Increase awareness and visibility

A primary goal of the communication strategy is to position PCP WISE as a leading initiative in the fields of innovative procurement, climate resilience, and EO-based water management. Many public authorities and potential suppliers are unfamiliar with the PCP model and its benefits, requiring clear, engaging, and accessible communication.

Strategic actions:

- Develop targeted messaging for different audience groups to explain the role of PCP in innovation procurement.
- Leverage multi-channel dissemination (website, social media, events, and media coverage) to maximise project visibility.
- Collaborate with EU institutions, environmental agencies, and procurement networks to extend outreach.

3.2.2. Drive stakeholder engagement and participation

PCP WISE depends on the active involvement of public buyers, suppliers, policymakers, and researchers to co-develop and test EO-based water management solutions. Communication plays a crucial role in ensuring that these stakeholders understand the project's objectives, benefits, and opportunities for participation.

Strategic actions:

- Organise co-creation workshops, info sessions, and matchmaking events to connect public buyers with suppliers.
- Build an interactive online community where stakeholders can exchange knowledge and insights.
- Develop engaging digital content (videos, infographics, webinars) to explain project developments and key findings.

3.2.3. Promote Knowledge Transfer and Capacity Building

One of the key objectives of PCP WISE is to mainstream the PCP process and encourage public sector organisations to adopt similar approaches for procuring innovative solutions. This requires educating public authorities and procurement professionals on how PCP works and providing them with the necessary tools and resources. Although the following strategic actions are to be developed in the context of other PCP WISE Work Packages – 4 and 5 notably – WP2 will play a key role in ensuring these activities are effectively communicated and promoted.

Strategic actions:

- Develop practical guidelines and best practice case studies on PCP in the water sector.
- Organise capacity-building sessions and policy dialogues to ensure that public authorities understand climate relevance and can replicate it into future PCP processes.

3.2.4. Support policy uptake and market adoption

For PCP WISE to achieve a long-lasting impact, its communication efforts must ensure that its results inform procurement policies at the EU and national levels and encourage market adoption of EO-based solutions. By providing feedback and recommendations to key decision-makers and industry players, PCP WISE can contribute to shaping future innovation procurement strategies.

Strategic actions:

- Develop white papers and a policy brief highlighting key recommendations based on project findings.
- Engage in high-level policy discussions with EU institutions and national governments through two webinars.

The success of PCP WISE depends on its ability to effectively communicate its objectives and achievements to key audiences. By raising awareness, engaging stakeholders, promoting knowledge transfer, and influencing policy, the communication strategy will help maximise the impact of the project and support the wider adoption of PCP-driven innovation in the water sector. A well-structured and proactive approach to communication will ensure that the project not only delivers results but also leaves a lasting legacy in procurement innovation and climate resilience.

3.3. Target audiences & key messages

As presented in section 2, the communication and dissemination strategy of the project answers to different needs and objectives, and therefore different audiences will be targeted. It is essential that different communities are addressed with messages and tools adapted to their interests and uses. This section answers the “to Whom to communicate and disseminate” and “What to communicate and disseminate” questions.

Effective communication requires a clear understanding of the audiences PCP WISE aims to engage and the key messages that will resonate with them. Given the project’s focus on PCP and EO for water management, stakeholders range from public procurers and technology providers to policymakers and the wider public. **Tailoring communication strategies to each group ensures maximum outreach, engagement, and impact.**

3.3.1. Target audiences

PCP WISE stakeholders are categorised into internal and external groups based on their roles and the three engagement levels in the project.

Figure 1: PCP WISE target audiences

3.3.1.1. Internal Stakeholders (directly involved in the project = TIER 1)

PCP WISE Buyers

This group represents the 12 public authorities participating as buyers led by the Lead Procurers (HwH) in the PCP WISE process. They define the challenges, coordinate joint procurement efforts, and implement innovative EO-based water management solutions. They

range from municipalities, water utilities, environmental agencies and regional public authorities.

PCP WISE Support Organisations

The 14 entities that provide strategic, technical, and administrative support to ensure the successful implementation of the PCP WISE process. They contribute expertise, policy alignment, and dissemination efforts. They range from research institutions and universities, EU-funded innovation networks, legal and procurement advisors, environmental and water governance bodies.

3.3.1.2. External Stakeholders (Engaged and Impacted by the Project= TIER 2 and TIER 3)

PCP WISE Suppliers

Companies, start-ups, and research organisations that develop and propose innovative EO-based solutions that respond to the challenges faced by the PCP WISE buyers, namely those which will respond to the call for tenders expected to be launched in September 2025. These actors are critical in delivering technologies that address climate resilience challenges. They include EO technology providers, data analytics companies, water management solution developers, Research & innovation SMEs and start-ups.

PCP WISE Replicators

Potential buyers outside the PCP WISE consortium who are interested in adopting the PCP WISE solutions in the future, integrating innovative solutions in their own procurement practices. Having them included in our strategy is of utmost importance as they will ensure the replicability of the model and processes created during the project. They include other municipalities and water agencies in Europe facing similar climate adaptation challenges, public procurers exploring PCP adoption, and national and regional authorities interested in innovative procurement as an effective solution to achieve climate resilience.

PCP WISE Followers

Any other organisation or individual interested in PCP WISE without being a buyer or supplier. These stakeholders can contribute to knowledge exchange, advocacy, and market uptake. They include policymakers at the EU and national levels, network and association of EO and space companies or agencies, procurement and innovation associations, other EU funded projects working on similar thematic areas as PCP WISE, media and opinion leaders (journalists, environmental influencers), environmental NGOs, the general public and civil society, among others etc.

3.3.2. Key messages

To ensure consistency across all communication efforts, PCP WISE aim to convey five core messages, adapted for each external target audiences.

3.3.2.1. Innovation Through Procurement

Message: PCP is a powerful tool for driving innovation in water management by enabling the public sector to act as a catalyst for technological advancement.

Target Audiences: PCP WISE Replicators, PCP WISE Followers.

Communication Channels: Website, digital flyer, white papers, policy brief, social media, newsletter, PCP WISE webstivals, conferences, Infoday webinars, videos, physical events.

3.3.2.2. Earth Observation for Smarter Water Solutions

Message: EO data provides cutting-edge insights for managing water resources, improving climate resilience, and reducing disaster risks.

Target Audiences: PCP WISE Suppliers, PCP WISE Replicators, PCP WISE Followers.

Communication Channels: Website, community platform, social media, digital flyer, newsletter, industry events, matchmaking events, Infoday webinars, videos, physical events.

3.3.2.3. Cross-Border Collaboration for Scalable Solutions

Message: By pooling resources and expertise, European buyers can achieve greater impact and cost efficiency through joint PCP initiatives.

Target Audiences: PCP WISE Replicators and PCP WISE Followers.

Communication Channels: Website, community platform, social media, infoDay, PCP WISE webstivals, participation in other events, policy brief, videos, digital flyer, physical events.

3.3.2.4. Public-Private Synergy to Accelerate Innovation

Message: PCP WISE fosters co-creation between public authorities and private sector innovators, ensuring solutions meet real-world needs.

Target Audiences: PCP WISE Suppliers, PCP WISE Replicators and PCP WISE Followers.

Communication Channels: Matchmaking on Community platform, policy brief, PCP WISE webstivals, participation in other events, newsletter, digital flyers, videos, physical events.

3.3.2.5. Climate Adaptation through Soil-Water Intelligence

Message: Enhancing climate resilience requires advanced soil-water intelligence systems that integrate EO data, real-time monitoring and predictive analytics. PCP WISE supports the development of innovative solutions to improve water resource management, mitigate extreme weather impacts, and support evidence-based decision-making for climate adaptation.

Target Audiences: PCP WISE Replicators, PCP WISE followers, PCP WISE Suppliers

Communication Channels: Community platform, policy brief, webstivals, participation in other events, policy brief, newsletter, digital flyers, videos, infoDay, etc.

3.3.3. Strategic Actions

- Refine messaging based on audience feedback (e.g., pilot test policy messages with public buyer representatives and pilot test industry messages with cluster organisation)
- Use storytelling techniques (real-world examples, testimonials) to make complex topics accessible, specifically to explain PCP WISE challenge and use cases
- Develop thematic campaigns, especially on social media (e.g., PCP for Climate Action, Water Management 4.0) to reinforce core messages.
- Set up an editorial calendar to plan social media content around project milestones and key events
- Provide local content by translating key materials such as digital flyers or a press release (not planned as part of PCP WISE materials but currently considered) into 5 local languages to increase accessibility
- Set up a curation system to track industry trends and events
- Establish connections and partnerships with key project, climate resilience and water management-related projects, -networks and -communities to ensure a pool of speakers and experts for events organisation

By aligning targeted messaging with audience needs, PCP WISE ensures that its communication efforts drive awareness, engagement, and long-term adoption of PCP-driven innovations in water management.

4. Communication channels & tools

As presented above in section 3, different target audiences have different uses and interests and therefore need to be addressed by a complementary set of tools. This section presents the tools set-up for the project communication and dissemination, as they further answer to the “**hoW** to communicate and disseminate” and “**What** to communicate and disseminate” questions.

4.1. Project branding and toolkit

4.1.1. Logo and visual identity

The **project logo** (Figure2) was designed by a professional designer with the goal to make the project easily recognisable and composed of elements representing the core aspects of PCP WISE: innovative public procurement, water management, EO.

Different versions of the PCP WISE logo have been produced and adapted to different backgrounds and displays (screens, print, white background, etc.). The logo is available both in pixel and vector formats and accessible by all project partners via the project shared platform.

The PCP WISE visual identity is based on the main logo colours and should be respected in all official communication materials provided digital or on paper. The colour codes are as follows:

Figure3: PCP WISE visual ID colour codes

4.1.2. Templates

Based on the PCP WISE visual identity and colour codes, a **Word document template** and a **PowerPoint template** have been developed to ensure coherence and a professional level of quality in terms of design and presentation in all project documents and communications. All project deliverables and public communications should use and strictly follow these templates and the guidelines provided in them.

For documents considered confidential, each partner is required to add the watermark “Confidential”.

Figure 4: PCP WISE Word template

As presented Figure 5, the PowerPoint template includes a set of slides with different layouts for specific uses including among other, a presentation cover slide, a table of contents/ agenda slide, a classic text content slide, a speaker quote slide, a timeline slide, several slides for displaying statistics and key figures, as well as for iconographies. At the end of the template, a set of seven illustrations that can be used in PowerPoint presentation as well as on other support are also provided.

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PCP&WISE Footer title 24/02/2025 18

«Ullamcorper ut facilisis pharetra montes porta rhoncus varius in.»

Author

PCP&WISE Footer title 24/02/2025 30

ICONS

Figure 5: PCP WISE PowerPoint template – Slides layouts

In addition, as depicted in Figure6 below, **two project banners** were developed for the LinkedIn page and the community platform. These banners or similar banners will be developed in the future for the use of events' registration pages for instance.

Figure6: PCP WISE banners for social media, community platform and events

4.1.3. Illustrations

The **project illustrations** were designed by a professional designer. They are available for the partners' use via the project shared platform and are based on the main logo colours. These illustrations can be used to enrich all project documents and deliverables.

The project illustrations are as follows:

Figure 7 : PCP WISE illustrations

4.1. Digital flyers & roll-ups

Two digital flyers [available on the PCP WISE page](#) of the PROTECT’s website have been designed to communicate about the project activities. These shall be used by all partners mainly for digital communication for promotion and information and guidance purposes to suppliers in particular, on the PCP, but may also be printed on demand to be distributed during events or meetings.

Figure 8: PCP WISE general flyer

The first flyer gives an overview of the project and its objectives and activities, whereas the second one is intended to be used by a technical audience. Six flyers will be developed throughout the project, including one that will present the results of PCP WISE at the end of the project.

PCP WISE

Water Management from Space

A New Approach for Global Climate Challenges

The Challenge We Face: Climate Change and Water Management

Climate change is causing severe global problems, such as droughts, floods, and disruptions in water supply. These issues also affect soil stability, drinking water quality, and increase the risk of wildfires, creating enormous potential for damage. European governments bear the responsibility for managing these risks.

To address these challenges, having accurate and timely management information is critical. This requires not only better maintenance systems but also leveraging smart monitoring and digital innovations. Tools like drones for inspections, AI-driven modelling, and satellite data are excellent examples of how technology can enrich existing knowledge. Water authorities must embrace these digital advancements to stay ahead of the challenges.

The Horizon Europe programme provides a unique opportunity to drive this digital transformation and tackle global climate challenges effectively.

Horizon Europe Programme: Funding Innovation for Water Management

In 2024, the EU allocated a €39M grant through the Horizon Europe programme to support applied research and development of satellite-based water management solutions. A project application named PCP WISE* was submitted for this funding and received approval in September 2024.

PCP WISE aims to deliver practical solutions to help water authorities improve their management capabilities. The below infographic highlights the project's goals and its potential benefits in addressing climate and water challenges.

*Estimation 2023 | Source: MCS 22/2024

PCP WISE: Monitoring the Soil-Water-Vegetation System

PCP WISE focuses on improving the monitoring of the local water balance in soil-water-vegetation systems, using remote sensing technology. This approach creates consistent and shareable data about water conditions.

- 1 Insight into (climate) trends, and current conditions
- 2 Getting to know the critical boundaries of our water balance system
- 3 Developing and stimulating climate models

With this updated information, local water managers can better prioritise actions based on Environmental Act guidelines. For example, when water shortages occur, decisions can be made to allocate resources effectively. The insights also support creating risk maps, which raise environmental awareness and help mitigate damage during water-related crises.

PCP WISE Action Plan

The European PCP WISE consortium of 26 local authorities, water authorities, and research institutions from 10 countries, has been formed to drive this initiative forward. To this end, Prof. Waterschapshuis is leading a group of 12 buyers who joined forces to undertake a Pre-Commercial Procurement procedure, supported by 14 additional partners providing assistance in this process.

In 2025 the consortium will launch a call for tenders inviting innovative market suppliers to respond and submit an offer to develop tailored solutions meeting the needs of the Buyers' group. These solutions will aim to enhance water system monitoring, improve insights, and advance early warning and monitoring technologies.

Currently, 22 use cases across five European countries — including five in the Netherlands — are being used to assess stakeholder needs. These use cases help shape the project's goals and refine the functional requirements of the solutions to be developed.

Benefits for Water Authorities

Water authorities are responsible for maintaining strong dikes and ensuring clean, sufficient water supplies. With the growing pressures of climate change and strict European regulations, experimenting with pilot projects has become essential.

PCP WISE supports the move toward data-driven operations and bears the ambition to prepare all water authorities for digital innovation by 2027. It offers a significant opportunity for the water sector to lead its digital transformation, build an international network, and share uniform cross-border data for a climate-resilient future.

By creating up-to-date local and sector-wide risk maps, water authorities can strengthen their ability to manage flood crises and potentially become leaders in European risk management.

*Proposal for the Customisation/Pre-operationalisation of Water management innovations from Space for European Climate Resilience

Figure 9 : PCP WISE technical flyer

In addition, **at least two roll-ups** are to be designed during the course of the project.

A **first roll-up** has been produced in two copies at the start of the project to promote the branding of the project, share information, and enhance visibility. A first copy was provided to the project coordinator and to be further circulated to other project partners who may attend physical events. A second copy will remain in the hands of GAC – the partner responsible for communication, dissemination and exploitation of activities. If needed, additional copies of the roll-up may be printed.

Figure 10: PCP WISE roll-up

The time for producing the second roll-up and its content will be discussed collectively with the project coordinator and partners.

4.2. Website

Before the official launch of the PCP WISE project, GAC created a dedicated PCP WISE page on the [PROTECT website](#) to provide a platform to communicate basic project information.

Figure 11: PCP WISE page on PROTECT website

The initial version of the **PCP WISE website** will be available by the end of M3 (March 2025). It will feature a responsive design, ensuring optimal display across all devices, from desktop computers to mobile phones.

Serving as the project's primary dissemination channel, the website will be integrated with social media and will host all public information and documentation generated throughout the project. This includes deliverables, event details and reports, newsletters, and links to relevant publications.

The website will be accessible at: <https://pcp-wise.eu/>

The following image showcases the draft homepage and the draft “About” page.

Figure 12: PCP WISE draft homepage and draft “About” page

The website serves as the primary vehicle for raising awareness of the PCP WISE project. It provides a general overview of the project’s objectives and consortium while offering public information on project activities, results, events and more. Additionally, it will guide stakeholders on ‘How to Get Involved’, grant access to the Community Platform, and include an option to subscribe to the project newsletter.

Designed in line with the PCP WISE branding, the website plays a key role in the project’s communication and information campaign. Its content will be continuously updated as new information becomes available.

To maximise outreach, the PCP WISE project will also promote and be promoted through other relevant web portals, creating synergies with other projects and initiatives such as the SPACE4CITIES, VALORADA, the Urban Agenda Partnership for Strategic and Innovation Procurement, and project partners' websites.

The project website is designed to engage all target audiences, including the general public. It will provide a clear introduction to the project and its potential impact, ensuring accessibility even for those unfamiliar with the topic.

4.3. Social media

4.3.1. LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the only social media network selected by the PCP WISE communication team. Other social media networks including X, Facebook and Instagram were considered, but considering the primary target audiences of the project – being technology providers and public procurers – they were deemed unsuitable to reach these target audiences.

The PCP WISE LinkedIn page set up as a company page is accessible at: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/PCP-WISE/>

Together with the project, it is a primary vehicle for targeted networking and to create a sustainable network in which the status of the project but also project outcomes can be shared.

Figure13: PCP WISE LinkedIn profile

An **editorial plan** has been developed to schedule LinkedIn posts and will also be used for website news, supporting the communication campaign towards market suppliers (potential bidders for the PCP call for tenders) external buyers (followers and potential replicators of the solutions), and other stakeholders (policymakers, researchers, innovation networks, general public, etc.).

Date	Channel	Content type	Topic/ Key message	Target audience	Call to action	Status
DD/MM/YYYY	LinkedIn	Announcement	Project launch – PCP WISE project kicked off!	General audience	Read more and download project flyer	Planned/ In progress/ Published
DD/MM/YYYY	LinkedIn	Call for action	Join the PCP WISE Community Platform	Market suppliers, External buyers, other stakeholders	Sign up now	Planned/ In progress/ Published

Figure 14: PCP WISE Editorial Plan template

As much as possible, LinkedIn posts and website news will follow clear content guidelines and best practices:

- messages will be kept concise and up to 300 words for LinkedIn posts and 300-600 words per news
- Links to related content (project documents, events, publications, etc.)
- Use of professional yet engaging tone
- engaging visuals (infographics, event banners, etc.)
- systematic hashtags such as #PCP WISE, #WaterInnovation, #InnovationProcurement, #Climate #Resilience, as well as specific hashtags depending on the content type
- tags of all project partners' organisations
- strong calls to action.

4.3.2. YouTube

YouTube is a popular video sharing platform where registered users can upload and share videos with anyone being able to view them, even without registering an account.

Targeted audiences will receive specific messages – through emailing, LinkedIn posts, project newsletter, in direct exchange – to invite them to watch the PCP WISE videos. As such, YouTube will only be a “deposit” platform for PCP WISE.

The PCP WISE YouTube account will be created once the first project video has been developed.

4.4. Videos

A minimum of 8 videos (of different duration, format, and style) will be developed throughout the course of the PCP WISE project and shall serve different purposes.

The **first video** will provide a 2-3min general, short, and concise presentation of the PCP WISE project, and will be available at M3. The following **six short videos** (up to 1min max) will each present the PCP use cases in a nutshell and will be developed during Phase 2 or Phase 3 of the PCP, during the live environment test phases. The **last video** will present PCP WISE main achievements and results and will be produced at the end of the project.

These videos will be made available online via a dedicated YouTube channel and disseminated via the website and the LinkedIn page. It will also be used by partners in their communication and dissemination activities (e.g., project presentation during external events).

4.5. Stakeholder Community Platform

The [PCP WISE Community Platform](#)³ is a dynamic, innovative digital collaboration platform, designed to foster engagement and collaboration among diverse communities and stakeholders. The PCP WISE Community Platform seamlessly integrates essential functionalities like event management (including webinars), news dissemination, group collaboration, and a powerful search engine, enabling stakeholders to contribute effectively and access information with ease.

The PCP WISE Community Platform serves as the primary gateway for all PCP WISE stakeholders to access relevant information and actively participate in collaborative activities. Built on the foundation of the ENRICH GLOBAL Collaboration Platform, it retains all the core features while incorporating specific functionalities and users of its predecessor platform – the [PROTECT Community Platform](#)⁴ – and is further tailored to the needs of the PCP WISE community.

The first version of the PCP WISE Community Platform has been launched in 2024, and its development is ongoing and will continue during the lifetime of the project. New features, defined according to the project's priorities, are continuously added.

The platform prioritises user engagement through intuitive features such as a personalised user profile system and a digest mechanism. The digest system, tailored to user preferences, delivers timely email notifications with summaries of newly published content, ensuring users remain updated on the latest developments. As a comprehensive collaboration platform, the PCP WISE Community Platform successfully combines cutting-edge digital tools with robust GDPR-compliant infrastructure, ensuring data privacy, sustainability, and reliability.

The PCP WISE Community platform is designed to host different communities of stakeholders including PCP WISE partners (buyers and support organisations) and external stakeholders

³ <https://egcp.enrich-global.eu/communities/pcp-wise>

⁴ <https://community.protect-pcp.eu/>

(external suppliers, external replicators, and external followers), and to organise outreach and engagement activities with such communities (e.g., awareness-raising and capacity building workshops trainings, group discussions, etc.).

These communities are part of the legacy of PROTECT and represent key assets in the success of PCP WISE. These communities have been reactivated before PCP WISE kicked off, and GAC invited PROTECT communities to join the PCP WISE Community Platform.

ENRICH GLOBAL COMMUNITY PLATFORM

Search by keywords Search

My communities Mélissa Campagno

PCP WISE

Pre-Commercial Procurement for Water management
Innovations from Space for European climate resilience

PCP-WISE
30 members

#climate #adaptation #space #observation #procurement #innovation

Home News Events Documents Members

Content management Administration

What is PCP-WISE about?
Building on the successes of PROTECT project, PCP-WISE is a unique, fully funded opportunity aimed at fostering partnerships between European public buyers and private sector innovators.
Our goal? To co-design innovative solutions for tackling water-related crises intensified by climate change.
Here is a snapshot of what PCP-WISE offers:

- €19M budget fully funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe programme.
- Collaboration among 11 public buyers ready to leverage the Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) instrument to acquire cutting-edge R&D services (up to TRL 8).
- Development of water intelligence systems using EO data, in-situ measurements, and AI analytics to prevent and mitigate water-related crises like floodings, fires, and subsidence both in urban and rural settings.

What's next?
In September 2025, the PCP-WISE buyers will launch a call for tenders. Market suppliers will be invited to submit proposals for the competitive process, which includes multiple stages of evaluation. Funding will be awarded to the most promising companies, with the entire PCP process a response in order to be selected and participate in the PCP competitive process extending until December 2027.

info-PCP-WISE(a)group-gac.com

Figure 15: PCP WISE Community Platform homepage

4.6. Newsletter

The PCP WISE newsletters will be sent via a professional emailing solution such as [MailChimp](#) integrating services in support of marketing emails, automated messages, and targeted campaigns and allowing easy customisation of templates, integration with social media sharing options, a monitoring system, and key statistics for every newsletter sent (number of messages opened, clicked, etc.).

Five newsletters will be released during the project, one every six months.

The **newsletter content preparation** will be initiated by GAC **two months before its publication**. GAC will propose the main newsletter's topics and further conduct an internal "call for ideas" to select additional newsletter's topics. Partners in charge of activities or having first-hand knowledge of the topics to be reported on will be requested to provide a ready-to-publish article within four weeks. GAC will then take care of editing and harmonising the contributions, setting up the newsletter, and circulating it to:

- Stakeholders having registered to the project mailing list; and
- PCP WISE partners for dissemination through their own networks.

The online version of the newsletter will be systematically published on the PCP WISE website and further shared via the LinkedIn page. Where possible, information on the newsletter or specific articles shall further be embedded in partners' institutional newsletters or related projects' communication channels.

A mailing list for **newsletter's subscribers' communication** will be set-up and **subscriptions shall be obtained by different means**, including:

- subscription via the project website;
- participants of PCP WISE events, online surveys and webinars, shall be invited to join the PCP WISE mailing list;
- promotion to subscribe via LinkedIn page; and
- existing individual contacts of project partners considered to be potentially interested in receiving the newsletter approached with a personal informative email communication allowing to subscribe.

All PCP WISE newsletter's subscriptions must be intentional and consent must be provided by each recipient. The whole process set up will be entirely GDPR compliant. Moreover, the newsletter will display an "unsubscribe" button and disclaimer, ensuring that all privacy requirements are met.

4.7. Project events

4.7.1. Planned events

4.7.1.1. Two face-to-face events

Under the supervision of GAC, **two face-to-face events** will be organised during the project and will, as much as possible, take place during external events and combine several activities of WP3, WP4 and WP5.

The first face-to-face event could be organised at M6 of the project to host a physical Open Market Consultation event or combined with the first external co-creation exploitation workshops (T2.3), WP5 face-to-face interviews and workshops or event with the in-person tabletop exercise event (T4.5.2). **The second face-to-face event** shall be the final project event and be organised at the end of the project M36 in order to present and disseminate the PCP WISE results to the largest possible audience of stakeholders.

Specific communications through LinkedIn, the website, and the community platform will be set up to **disseminate the results of each face-to-face event**.

4.7.1.2. Webstivals

Similarly, GAC will drive the organisation of **two webstivals** (tentatively proposed at M8 and at M18) aimed at widely communicating and promoting the project's objectives, activities and results, and combining as much as possible several activities of WP3, WP4 and WP5.

These online events will be **engaging and dynamic**, as they will be **divided into a series of different sessions** – addressing local and regional public authorities, policy makers, R&I stakeholders, climate services providers, sustainable communities and citizens associations – allowing for interactive and networking activities. They will also serve to engage with relevant projects/initiatives in order to develop the project's ecosystem relations and create fruitful synergies.

Tentatively, **the first webstival** shall serve to promote the upcoming PCP WISE call for tenders and as such combine a mix of PCP online preparatory activities (e.g., InfoDays, Open Market Consultations, etc.) and awareness-raising and capacity building activities in the form of thematic webinars (e.g., unpacking the PCP approach, Earth Observation contribution to innovative Water Intelligence climate services, etc.)

The concept and timing of **the second webstival** will be discussed and agreed with project partners and defined as part of the second communication activities update.

4.7.1.3. Scalability and replicability workshops

Six online scalability and replicability workshops will be organised during the project to collect feedback and opinions on the scalability, interoperability and replicability aspects of the PCP WISE solutions, and maximise their potential uptake by a pool of external buyers.

These workshops will further serve to **seek recommendations for developing a roadmap for the scaling up the PCP-WISE's solutions** in new local contexts. Selected PCP WISE suppliers may be invited to participate in the scalability and replicability workshops to present their solutions to other buyers.

GAC is responsible for the organisation of the six online scalability and replicability workshops with the support of WP2 task leaders and all other project partners, to define content (e.g., agenda and speakers).

4.7.2. External events

In addition to events organised as part of the PCP WISE project, **all project partners will take part in other events** organised by external stakeholders or as part of other projects they participate in. Participation to external events where the PCP WISE project will be promoted in different forms (presentations, networking, flyers distribution, pitch, etc.) will be supervised and previously agreed with GAC.

GAC is responsible for centralising all relevant events where PCP WISE could be promoted and reaching out to relevant PCP WISE partners best positioned to attend the event, depending of

the location of the event, the target audience, the communication and dissemination activity to carry out during the event, etc.

Before PCP WISE was officially launched, project partners participated in events taking place in Fall 2024 with a view to raising awareness of the main target audiences, namely public buyers and providers of EO data and climate services, about the project activities and to maintain the momentum created by the PROTECT project.

Name of Event	Dates	Type of Event	Location	Lead Partner
Flash Flood Breaker	26-29/09/2024	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Duisburg, Germany	STOWA
New Space Economy [Session dedicated to "Commercial Space-based Solutions 4Water"]	01-02/10/2024	Participation to a Conference	Barcelona, Spain	BRB
Space for Food Security – Next Perspectives	02/10/2024	Participation to a Conference	The Hague, The Netherlands	STOWA
NEREUS – European Regional Symposium	02-03/10/2024	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Toulouse, France	AV
EuroGEO	08-10/10/2024	Participation to a Conference	Krakow, Poland	CKIC
Mission Projects Seminar: Introducing New Projects to the EU Mission Community	15/10/2024	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU projects	Online	BRB
Smart City World Congress	05-07/11/2024	Participation to a Conference	Barcelona, Spain	IEEC

Table 1: External events used for PCP WISE outreach in 2024

Whilst the outreach during external events will be based on opportunities arising during the project runtime, the following events (running until July 2025) have already been identified and PCP WISE's participation is currently being discussed or prepared:

Name of Event	Dates	Type of Event	Location	Lead Partner
Sharing lessons learnt from PCPs by Forum Virium	09/01/2025	Organisation of a workshop	Online	BRB
Winter Satellite Workshop	21/01 – 23/02/2025	Participation to a conference	Helsinki, Finland	FVH
Adra-e project's workshop on how to facilitate the access of innovative start-ups and SMEs	04/02/2025	Participation to a workshop	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	HAA

Name of Event	Dates	Type of Event	Location	Lead Partner
to the public procurement market				
EU Mission Adaptation Community Event: Building Back Better	11/02/2025	Participation to a workshop	Online	GAC
WIP4adapt webinar 'Public procurement in building'	20/02/2025	Participation to a workshop	Online	CKIC
INNOVATION PROCUREMENT UPTAKE: Overcoming barriers in the legal framework that hamper wider implementation of innovation procurement	20/02/2025	Promotion of PCP WISE at a webinar organised by the EC on Innovation Procurement.	Online	CPS
Satellite-based Services for Disaster Risk Management in Spain	26/02/2025	Participation to a conference	Barcelona, Spain	IEEC
Climateurope2 Webstival Climate services for cities. Shaping climate adaptation and mitigation actions	11-12/03/2025	Participation to a workshop	Online	BRB
MIP4Adapt webinar 'Tips for creating your awareness-raising campaigns'	12/03/2025	Participation to a workshop	Online	GAC
Water Projects Europe at AQUATECH2025	12/03/2025	Participation to a workshop	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	GAC
MIP4adapt webinar 'Assessing climate risk and vulnerabilities'	20/03/2025	Participation to a workshop	Online	CKIC
New Space & Solutions	17-21/03/2025	Participation to a conference	Sevilla, Spain	BRB
MIP4Adapt webinar 'Leveraging funding for climate adaptation'	26/03/2025	Participation to a workshop	Online	GAC
Water Market Europe 2025	27/03/2025	Participation to a workshop	Girona, Spain	GAC
Dutch Water info day	27/03/2025	Participation to a workshop	The Hague, The Netherlands	STOWA
Dutch Water info day	01-02/04/2025	Participation to a workshop	Hasselt, The Netherlands	STOWA
European Regulation of Climate Services: A Dialogue with Private Providers	28-29/04/2025	Participation to a conference	Barcelona, Spain	GAC
GEO Global Forum 2025	05-09/05/2025	Participation to a conference	Rome, Italy	GAC
Urban Future Poland 2025	21-23/05/2025	Participation to a conference	Lodz, Poland	GAC
EU Industry Days	05-06/06/2025	Participation to a conference	Rzeszow, Poland	GAC

Name of Event	Dates	Type of Event	Location	Lead Partner
EXPANDEO 2025	11-12/06/2025	Participation to a conference	Brussels, Belgium	GAC
7th Biennial European Conference on Climate Change Adaptation (ECCA2025)	16-18/06/2025	Participation to a conference	Rimini, Italy	GAC
European Resilience Forum 2025 (EURESFO)	25-27/06/2025	Participation to a conference	Rotterdam, The Netherlands	GAC
ESA Living Planet Symposium 2025	23-27/06/2025	Participation to a conference	Vienna, Austria	GAC
New Space Economy Congress	03-04/07/2025	Participation to a conference	Barcelona, Spain	TBD

Table 2: External events used for PCP WISE outreach in 2025

4.8. Other communication activities

4.8.1. White papers

Two **white papers** will be produced as part of the exploitation task (Task 2.3). One will present the opportunities offered to suppliers to use Venture Capital (VC) to support the commercialisation of the solutions, and a second presenting other funding opportunities available to procurers.

The white paper is strategically chosen as the ideal format for dual purposes within the PCP WISE project due to its ability to provide in-depth, authoritative analysis tailored to specific audiences.

For VCs, the white paper format allows for a detailed presentation of the project's successful use cases, offering comprehensive insights into the technical and market potential of the innovations. This depth of analysis is essential for investors who require thorough, evidence-based information to make informed decisions. Other formats, such as brochures or presentations, may not provide the same level of detail and credibility needed to attract investment. Thus, the white paper serves as the most effective tool for articulating compelling investment opportunities, positioning the project's developments as attractive and credible prospects.

For public procurers, the white paper is the optimal choice because it can systematically outline the complexities of the funding landscape, providing a structured and detailed overview of available resources. This format is particularly effective in delivering actionable insights into how these funding opportunities can be leveraged to sustain and expand the innovative solutions developed in the project. Unlike simpler communication tools like fact sheets or newsletters, the white paper allows for a thorough exploration of these funding mechanisms, ensuring that procurers are well equipped to navigate the post-project funding.

The second White Paper planned during PCP WISE, White paper on Stakeholder's outreach and engagement's achievements, is due at the end of the project (M35) and will serve to disseminate the results and possible synergies developed during the Stakeholder Outreach activities. As the project goes on, a strong European network shall be created and will necessarily have an impact on the PCP and on the project overall. To ensure this impact is as broad as possible, it is necessary to demonstrate the strength of this new ecosystem specific to the project and the opportunities that exist in Europe in this respect. It is from this particular angle that the White Paper will be written and disseminated.

4.8.2. Policy brief

As agreed in the GA, a Policy Brief is foreseen in M34 of the project. This deliverable (D2.12) will serve as a short document of about two to three pages showcasing key findings and recommendations at the final stage of the project.

Even though the contents of the above-referred deliverable are likely to be slightly modified from the time in which this report is produced until the date in which D2.12 will be released, the following are the main points that could be included in the Policy Brief:

- Key insights and recommendations: by M34, the project will be reaching its end date and, therefore, the consortium will have learned important lessons from the whole PCP process. The main aim of the Policy Brief will be to summarise these lessons learnt and include the key recommendations arisen from them.
- Brief presentation of engaged stakeholders: the PCP WISE Policy Brief will also give an overview of the reached stakeholders, their role, contributions and outcomes.
- Replicability: the deliverable will aim at how the results and lessons learned during the PCP WISE project can be replicated and implemented in other similar projects or actions. It will also care about its replicability in real conditions, following the lessons learned after the implementation of the PCP process.
- Promote the use of the PCP tool to accelerate innovation in the public sector: one of the key elements as to show to the public sector organisations that a PCP instrument serves as a way of covering public needs in a more competitive way.

5. Roles and responsibilities

Partners have agreed on the following roles regarding PCP WISE's communication and dissemination activities. The Work Package 2 is led by G.A.C. Group (GAC) with the support of Aerospace Valley (AV) and Evenflow (EVF). All partners will work closely with the Work Package leader to provide input to all the communication and dissemination activities, therefore playing an important role in spreading information. The work task responsibilities are distributed as follows:

GAC, the Work Package leader

Leads the management and coordination of the Work Package including:

- Setting up of the communication strategy.
- Monitoring and coordinating the dissemination and communication activities throughout Europe.
- Interacting with all partners for the dissemination and communication activities.
- Stimulating partners to provide communication and dissemination input, such as news for publication on the project website or social media, newsletters, etc.

Decides and drives the dissemination and communication activities, including:

- Providing text of relevant news and publications related to general project activities.
- Ensuring quality control of the information provided.
- Creation of a visual identity and provision of templates (Word and PowerPoint).
- Production of promotional material based on the contributions from partners.
- Set up and update of the project website; and
- Managing the PCP WISE social media account, YouTube channel, and project website and Community Platform.

Aerospace Valley and Evenflow, The Work Package Task Leaders

Supports the implementation of the Work Package, including:

- Identifying and mapping key project stakeholders and continuously expanding this mapping (EVF)
- Establishing strategies and specific request to identify additional relevant project stakeholders (EVF)
- Setting up the outreach strategy of the project and performing all outreach activities
- Ensuring liaison with relevant initiatives at European, national and local levels
- Supporting the Task 2.1 and providing relevant speaker names for events organisations and outreach activities

All project partners

All partners shall:

- Use the project's visual identity for any communication on the project.
- Provide contributions/material for public use on the project website and communication material upon request (e.g., use case descriptions, logos, etc.).

- Provide news and/or communications on important activities and achievements related to PCP WISE.
- Inform GAC about possible participation in conferences, workshops, etc. related to PCP WISE.
- Provide short texts about participation in events for the news section of the project website (accompanied by related links and pictures whenever available).
- Disseminate PCP WISE information, materials and deliverables through their channels and networks.
- Regularly inform GAC about which communication channels and networks were used; and
- Provide the required information for the reporting to the European Commission

The partners will fulfil their responsibilities autonomously and provide input in time to all the dissemination activities driven by GAC; but also, proactively disseminate information on the project activities and outcomes via their channels and networks. The entire consortium is playing an important role in disseminating information.

All partners will be asked to report on a regular basis on their dissemination and communication activities, using a template (Excel file already provided by GAC and available on the Teams environment). An update on communication and dissemination activities reported by the partners will be part of the agenda of the plenary meetings.

A list of dedicated communication/dissemination contacts within the project partners will be set up and is maintained by GAC.

6. Monitoring and evaluation

To measure the effectiveness of PCP WISE’s communication strategy, clear procedures will need to be followed by partners and success indicators will be tracked throughout the project.

6.1. Monitoring of communication and dissemination activities

To ensure the communication and dissemination strategy stays up to date, an internal planning, coordination and monitoring process shall be followed. All partners must report on their communication and dissemination activities and opportunities. GAC as Work Package leader will regularly check the progress and, if needed, adjust the planning of communication and dissemination activities. GAC will also supervise all activities and provide strategic direction when needed. GAC will further coordinate the collection of updates and news content from partners to produce news on the project website and posts on social media pages.

A single ‘Communication and Dissemination (C&D) planning and monitoring’ Excel file was developed by GAC and is to be used by all partners to **plan, coordinate and report** on all communication and dissemination activities, as well as on the preparation and publishing of news and social media posts. This Excel file will be weekly reviewed and updated by GAC with the support of consortium partners, indicating:

- Actions
- Person in charge
- Channel to be used
- Purpose of the action
- Content to be conveyed
- Targeted audience
- Etc.

This file will also provide a monthly planning of communication and dissemination activities and actions to be taken, that will be constantly updated.

6.2. Key Performance Indicators

Measurable target and KPIs are set for the communication and dissemination activities. These indicators will assess the reach, engagement, and impact of communication activities and help refined the strategy if needed.

#	KPI	Target	WP
1	Number of stakeholders consulted throughout the project	200+	2
2	Number of website visitors (by the end of 3rd year)	4000+	2
3	Number of news posted on the Website per year	20	2

4	Number of followers on LinkedIn	300+	2
5	Number of posts on LinkedIn per year	40	2
6	Number of events organised online or physical events	25+	2
7	Number of newsletters	5	2
8	Number of newsletters subscribers	100+	2
9	Number of events in which the project partners participate in/ attend	30+	2
10	Number of digital flyers	6+	2
11	Number of videos	8	2
12	Number of roll-ups	2	2
13	Number of members in the PCP WISE Community Platform	60	2
14	Number of white papers	2	2
15	Number of investors reached	20+	2

Table 3: PCP WISE Communication KPIs

7. Conclusion

This deliverable provides a framework based on the 6W methodology to all consortium partners for promoting PCP WISE's project activities and maximising their impacts through planned, coordinated and monitored communication and dissemination activities.

It also describes the roles and responsibilities of partners in this regard and further identifies the project target audiences and the key messages to be delivered to them. While GAC is the Work Package leader and AV and EVF are Task leaders, all project partners will be continuously involved in the communication and dissemination activities.

The communication strategy and toolkit outlined in this report will be updated and adjusted if needed in the context of the first communication activities update to be delivered at M18.